

Impact of Nuclear Data Uncertainties of ^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^{239}Pu in Benchmarks Representative of Small Fast Reactors

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ABSTRACT

This work presents an uncertainty quantification study assessing the impact of nuclear data (ND) covariances of ^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^{239}Pu on benchmarks representative of small fast reactors. The analyzed benchmarks are GODIVA, FLATTOP-25, JEZEBEL, FLATTOP-Pu, BIGTEN, and ZEBRA-8H. Uncertainties of k_{eff} are evaluated using the NDaST tool and the sandwich methodology, combining sensitivity coefficients with cross-section covariance data. Sensitivities are obtained with MCNP6.3, while covariance data are taken from the JEFF-3.3/4.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.0/1 libraries. The results show that calculated biases (C-E) are largely encompassed by propagated ND uncertainties, although differences are observed among libraries. JEFF-3.3/4.0 yields larger uncertainties for ^{235}U and ^{238}U benchmarks. In Pu benchmarks, ENDF/B-VIII.1 shows a further reduction in k_{eff} uncertainty compared to ENDF/B-VIII.0, mainly due to reduced uncertainties in ^{239}Pu prompt fission neutron spectra and fission reaction. Although ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 exhibit similar relative standard deviations for ^{238}U reactions, changes in correlations lead to lower k_{eff} uncertainties in ENDF/B-VIII.1. The contribution of angular distribution covariances (MF34) to k_{eff} uncertainty is also quantified, showing reductions for ^{235}U and ^{238}U in ENDF/B-VIII.1. Finally, a k_{eff} perturbation analysis reveals that, for some reactions (e.g. $^{238}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ in BIGTEN), discrepancies between libraries exceed the evaluated uncertainties. Overall, this study improves understanding of ND uncertainty propagation in fast systems and supports efforts to improve evaluated ND for reactor applications.

Keywords: Covariance, nuclear data uncertainty, fast reactors

1. INTRODUCTION

Previous studies were focused on the performance of nuclear data libraries for systems representative of small-size fast reactors [1]; therefore a set of benchmarks were selected from the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) Handbook [2]:

- Spherical metal assemblies with highly enriched uranium (GODIVA⁽¹⁾/HMF001⁽²⁾, FLATTOP-25/TOPSY⁽¹⁾/HMF028⁽²⁾) and plutonium (JEZEBEL/PMF001, FLATTOP-Pu/POPSY/PMF006). These assemblies are either bare systems or a sphere surrounded by a thick depleted uranium reflector.
- BIGTEN⁽¹⁾/IMF007⁽²⁾ and ZEBRA-8H/MMF008.c7 are also included describing systems with fast energy neutron spectrum having a large amount of ^{235}U and ^{238}U .

In this work, an uncertainty quantification is performed to assess the impact of differences in covariances among nuclear data libraries: JEFF-3.3/4.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.0/1. Covariance data, processed with NJOY2016.74 into a compact and tabulated BOXER format, were sandwiched with benchmark sensitivities using the NDaST [3] tool (www.oecd-nea.org/ndast). Thus, k_{eff} uncertainties for the six benchmarks with the processed covariance data in ^{235}U , ^{238}U and ^{239}Pu are calculated.

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^(1,2) Naming used by Keepin⁽¹⁾, and ICSBEP/IRPhEP⁽²⁾

2. SENSITIVITY COEFFICIENTS

A relative sensitivity “S” of the multiplication factor k_{eff} with respect to a certain microscopic cross section “x” of a certain nuclide “i” in a certain energy group “g”, is defined as follows:

$$S_{x,g}^i = \frac{\frac{\Delta k}{k}}{\frac{\Delta \sigma_{x,g}^i}{\sigma_{x,g}^i}}$$

For all the benchmarks considered, sensitivity coefficients are predicted with MCNP6.3 [4] using the MCNP/KSEN card. A total number of 10^9 active neutron histories were requested to reduce the statistical uncertainty in these tallies. These sensitivities are calculated with the JEFF-3.3 nuclear data library in 70 energy groups. In this work, the following sensitivities have been defined (MT values are also given which correspond to the MCNP/KSEN card terminology):

- Reaction cross-section sensitivities: elastic scattering (MT=2) and inelastic scattering (MT=4), (n,2n) (MT=16), fission (MT=18) and (n,gamma) (MT=102)
- Total neutron multiplicity (nubar) (MT=452)
- Prompt fission neutron spectra (PFNS/chi) (MT= -1018, it corresponds to MF5/MT18 in ENDF-102)
- Angular dependence of the scattering (elastic and inelastic) data to Legendre terms P_1 to P_5
- Finally, elastic (MT= -1002, it is MF4/MT2) and inelastic (MT= -1004, it is MF4/MT4) scattering laws

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show k_{eff} sensitivity coefficients for (n,elastic)/Legendre- P_1 and (n,fission) of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu , respectively. Figure 3 shows sensitivities for (n,elastic)/Legendre- P_1 and (n,n') of ^{238}U .

Figure 1. Sensitivity to Legendre- P_1 (a) and (n,fission) (b) for ^{235}U

Figure 2. Sensitivity to Legendre- P_1 (a) and (n,fission) (b) for ^{239}Pu

Figure 3. Sensitivity to Legendre- P_1 (a) and $(n,inelastic)$ (b) for ^{238}U

3. UNCERTAINTY QUANTIFICATION

Sensitivities are used for evaluating uncertainties of k_{eff} through the so-called sandwich formula, i.e., by multiplying the cross-section covariance matrices from the right and left by the corresponding partial sensitivity vector and its transpose, respectively.

For calculating these nuclear data uncertainties, covariance matrices for (n,n) , (n,n') , $(n,2n)$, $(n,fission)$, (n,γ) , nubar and chi were processed in 33 energy groups from the corresponding ENDF files. PFNS covariances are processed with NJOY2016.74 at $E_{\text{incident}} = 1$ MeV.

Based on these covariance data and the sensitivity vectors of the considered benchmarks, total uncertainties as well as contributions from individual cross sections were calculated with NDaST.

A summary of these uncertainty results is presented in Table 1 where the predicted k_{eff} bias (C-E) with different nuclear data libraries is shown in comparison with the experimental uncertainty and the calculated uncertainty caused by the nuclear covariance data. It is seen that the k_{eff} bias (C-E) are broadly covered by the relative uncertainties originating from the respective covariance data.

Table I. Summary of results including the bias, the experimental benchmark uncertainties and calculated uncertainties caused by nuclear data covariances (values in pcm).

		Godiva	Flattop-25	Jezebel	Flattop-Pu	BigTen	Zebra-8H
Benchmark	Exp. Unc (pcm)	100	300	110	300	70	240
JEFF3.3	Bias (C-E)	20	401	21	340	38	-370
	ND uncert	1366	1483	689	1036	1829	2231
JEFF4.0	Bias (C-E)	-93	-33	78	39	5	-605
	ND uncert	1366	1483	689	1036	1829	2231
ENDF/B-VIII.0	Bias (C-E)	5	90	74	-19	-30	-666
	ND uncert	1039	1087	1009	1050	1044	1424
ENDF/B-VIII.1	Bias (C-E)	0	90	13	2	0	-585
	ND uncert	1020	980	732	719	1006	1328

An uncertainty quantification assessment of k_{eff} caused by nuclear data uncertainties of ^{235}U , ^{238}U and ^{239}Pu is presented in Table II, Table III and Table IV. The row "Sum" contains full correlations between reactions. The uncertainty quantification is given for JEFF-4.0 (=JEFF-3.3), ENDF/B-VIII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0. All covariance results were obtained with sensitivities calculated with JEFF-3.3. Although this is not completely consistent, a minor influence in the results is expected, and sensitivity calculations with other libraries are not required. The advantage is to separate out the differences in covariance matrix evaluations.

Table II. Uncertainty quantification due to nuclear data uncertainties: JEFF-4.0=JEFF-3.3 (values in pcm).

		Godiva	Flattop-25	Jezebel	Flattop-Pu	BigTen	Zebra-8H
U235	elastic	118	38	0	1	5	4
	inelastic	695	324	0	3	58	136
	n,2n	16	9	0	0	0	1
	fission	659	713	0	15	1074	1218
	gamma	400	479	0	5	466	446
	nubar	508	481	0	6	410	406
	chi	404	502	0	12	916	965
	Sum U235=	1365	1277	0	23	1577	1689
U238	elastic	6	141	0	125	126	28
	inelastic	38	444	0	453	506	1326
	n,2n	1	6	0	7	10	17
	fission	18	148	0	155	390	394
	gamma	5	129	0	110	614	860
	nubar	9	73	0	73	232	249
	chi	4	79	0	84	329	371
	Sum U238=	60	754	0	745	926	1458
Pu239	elastic	0	0	101	35	0	0
	inelastic	0	0	131	43	0	0
	n,2n	0	0	5	3	0	0
	fission	0	0	303	279	0	0
	gamma	0	0	29	45	0	0
	nubar	0	0	409	382	0	0
	chi	0	0	509	553	0	0
	Sum Pu239=	0	0	689	720	0	0
Sum U235+U238+Pu239=	1366	1483	689	1036	1829	2231	

Table III. Uncertainty quantification due to nuclear data uncertainties: ENDF/B-VIII.0 (values in pcm)

		Godiva	Flattop-25	Jezebel	Flattop-Pu	BigTen	Zebra-8H
U235	elastic	291	98	0	2	14	4
	inelastic	236	100	0	1	34	43
	n,2n	22	13	0	0	1	1
	fission	785	691	0	9	607	621
	gamma	295	341	0	4	316	299
	nubar	399	373	0	4	311	310
	chi	138	158	0	5	366	415
	Sum U235=	1038	897	0	12	836	855
U238	elastic	18	354	0	342	262	35
	inelastic	21	282	0	266	267	786
	n,2n	1	3	0	4	6	10
	fission	8	66	0	69	178	182
	gamma	2	80	0	67	396	583
	nubar	11	92	0	92	293	315
	chi	3	59	0	62	243	274
	Sum U238=	42	614	0	598	625	1139
Pu239	elastic	0	0	528	201	0	0
	inelastic	0	0	679	236	0	0
	n,2n	0	0	9	5	0	0
	fission	0	0	905	786	0	0
	gamma	0	0	63	100	0	0
	nubar	0	0	320	270	0	0
	chi	0	0	217	232	0	0
	Sum Pu239=	0	0	1009	863	0	0
Sum U235+U238+Pu239=	1039	1087	1009	1050	1044	1424	

Table IV. Uncertainty quantification due to nuclear data uncertainties: ENDF/B-VIII.1 (values in pcm)

		Godiva	Flattop-25	Jezebel	Flattop-Pu	BIG TEN	Zebra-8H
U235	elastic	291	98	0	2	14	4
	inelastic	236	100	0	1	34	43
	n,2n	22	13	0	0	1	1
	fission	785	691	0	9	607	621
	gamma	295	341	0	4	316	299
	nubar	383	337	0	3	248	243
	chi	90	101	0	3	224	253
	Sum U235=	1020	873	0	11	765	773
U238	elastic	18	354	0	342	262	35
	inelastic	21	282	0	266	267	786
	n,2n	1	3	0	4	6	10
	fission	8	66	0	69	178	182
	gamma	2	80	0	67	396	582
	nubar	11	92	0	92	293	315
	chi	3	59	0	62	243	274
	Sum U238=	31	445	0	436	653	1079
Pu239	elastic	0	0	393	156	0	0
	inelastic	0	0	578	191	0	0
	n,2n	0	0	3	2	0	0
	fission	0	0	549	426	0	0
	gamma	0	0	18	29	0	0
	nubar	0	0	418	370	0	0
	chi	0	0	95	100	0	0
	Sum Pu239=	0	0	732	572	0	0
Sum U235+U238+Pu239=	1020	980	732	719	1006	1328	

A comparison of Tables II, III and IV shows larger uncertainties with JEFF-3.3/JEFF-4.0 than for ENDF/B-VIII.0/1 for all $^{235}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ benchmarks. For Pu benchmarks, a significant reduction in uncertainty is shown between ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1. For JEFF-3.3/JEFF-4.0, there is a remarkably large uncertainty for BigTen and ZEBRA-8H because of the large uncertainties in $^{235}\text{U}/(\text{n},\text{fission})$ and chi and $^{238}\text{U}/(\text{n},\text{gamma})$ and $(\text{n},\text{inelastic})$.

Tables III and IV show an interesting comparison from ENDF/B-VIII.0 to ENDF/B-VIII.1:

- Note that k_{eff} uncertainties due to PFNS covariances dropped significantly in ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu which is explained by inclusion of high-precision experimental data in the ENDF/B-VIII.1 [5].
- The total k_{eff} uncertainty in Pu benchmarks due to ^{239}Pu significantly dropped due to fission and elastic uncertainties. Figure 4 shows a comparison of evaluated uncertainties for PFNS and $(\text{n},\text{fission})$ of ^{239}Pu in different ENDF/B evaluations. It is also observed that there is a slightly increased k_{eff} uncertainty due to neutron multiplicity.
- For ^{235}U benchmarks, k_{eff} uncertainties due to ^{235}U are fairly similar.
- A significant drop in uncertainty for ^{238}U is observed due to different ^{238}U correlations between cross sections. The correlations exceeding ± 1 between (n,n) - (n,n') , (n,n') - (n,f) and (n,n') - (n,gamma) were corrected in ENDF/B-VIII.1 [6]. This can be seen in Figure 5 which presents a comparison of correlation between $^{238}\text{U}(\text{n},\text{n})$ and $^{238}\text{U}(\text{n},\text{n}')$ for ENDF/B-VIII.0 and VIII.1.

3.1. Uncertainty Quantification in Angular Distributions

Finally, uncertainty quantification is performed for the elastic angular distributions. Covariance data for elastic angular distributions in the evaluated files are included in file MF34. It has been processed with NJOY2016.74 in 70 energy groups. Here, the sensitivities for the P_1 are used in the sandwich formula, to estimate the uncertainty in k_{eff} , only ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 have been included because they contain MF34 for the three files ^{235}U , ^{238}U and ^{239}Pu . A summary of results is presented in Table V. As observed, these uncertainties are not negligible, showing a significant drop for ^{235}U and ^{238}U in ENDF/B-VIII.1.

Figure 4. Evaluated Uncertainties (in relative standard deviation in %) for ^{239}Pu PFNS for $E_{\text{inc}}=1$ MeV (a) and $(n,fission)$ (b) for different ENDF/B evaluations and JEFF-4.0

Figure 5. Evaluated ^{238}U correlations for $(n,n)-(n,n')$ in ENDF/B-VIII.0 (a) and ENDF/B-VIII.1 (b)

Table V. Summary of k_{eff} uncertainties results using covariances of nuclear data in MF34

		Godiva	Flattop-25	Jezebel	Flattop-Pu	BigTen	Zebra-8H
ENDF/B-VIII.0	U235	422	162	0	2	13	4
	U238	17	366	0	469	163	7
	Pu239	0	0	161	63	0	0
	Sum All=	422	400	161	473	163	9
ENDF/B-VIII.1	U235	225	87	0	1	9	2
	U238	9	191	0	218	108	3
	Pu239	0	0	161	63	0	0
	Sum All=	225	210	161	226	108	3

4. Deviation Analysis versus Uncertainty Quantification

In this Section, we perform an individual analysis of the k_{eff} deviations (or perturbations) from nuclear data in JEFF-3.3 (J33) to ENDF/B-VIII.0 (E80). This perturbation analysis for each reaction channel is completed with its uncertainty quantification. Table VI highlights the nuclear data with the largest deviations in k_{eff} caused by the differences between JEFF-3.3 (J33) and ENDF/B-VIII.0 (E80).

These deviations or perturbations in k_{eff} can be computed using direct substitutions of MF/MT in the evaluated files. For these substitutions no other constraints are taken into account. Updated files with the corresponding exchanged data are processed with NJOY to create modified ACE formatted libraries. Additional MCNP calculations are needed to yield the k_{eff} changes resulting from each individual change in cross section. Table VI, column 3, shows the impact of these substitutions of MF/MT in k_{eff} .

Additionally, a linear approximation can be used with sensitivity analysis to predict k_{eff} perturbation caused by replacing cross sections of the JEFF-3.3 library with cross sections of ENDF/B-VIII.0:

$$\left(\frac{\Delta k_{eff}}{k_{eff}}\right)_x^i \cong \sum_{g=1}^G S_{x,g,JEFF33}^i \cdot \frac{\sigma_{x,g,E80}^i - \sigma_{x,g,J33}^i}{\sigma_{x,g,J33}^i}$$

Here:

- Δk is the change of the k_{eff} caused by replacing a cross-section $\sigma_{x,g,J33}^i$ of the JEFF-3.3 library with the cross-section $\sigma_{x,g,E80}^i$ of ENDF/B-VIII.0 (see values in column 4 of Table VI).
- The summation runs over the energy groups $1, \dots, G$.
- “S” denotes the sensitivity vector of k_{eff} to the cross section $\sigma_{x,g}^i$. These sensitivities are calculated with the JEFF-3.3 nuclear data library.

For most of the reactions, Δk results obtained with sensitivity analysis and direct substitution of MF/MT yield reasonable agreement, except for the $^{235}\text{U}(n,n')$. For this reaction, the Secondary Energy Distributions (SED) differ considerably between JEFF-3.3 and ENDF/B-VIII.0 and this requires the use of a matrix-formed sensitivity coefficient jointly with the relative change of scattering matrices [1].

In Table VI, these k_{eff} deviations are compared with the k_{eff} uncertainties caused by the respective nuclear covariance data, given in the columns labeled as “uncertainty”. Here, it is noticeable that in some cases, the individual contributions to the library deviations are significantly higher than the respective nuclear data uncertainty contributions, see the case of $^{239}\text{Pu}(n,n')$ in Jezebel and $^{238}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ in BigTen and ZEBRA-8H.

Table VI. Main contributions (> 100 pcm) to the JEFF-3.3 (“J33”) vs ENDF/B-VIII.0 (“E80”) multiplication factor deviations of the set of benchmarks in pcm, in comparison with the contributions to the uncertainties from the nuclear covariance data (values in pcm).

Case	Main contributor	E80/J33* Substitution MF/MT	E80/J33 Perturbation S/A	JEF-3.3 =JEFF-4.0 uncertainty	ENDF/B- VIII.0 uncertainty	ENDF/B- VIII.1 uncertainty
Godiva	U235(n,n')	-234	22	695	236	236
	U235(n,gamma)	160	162	400	295	295
	U235(nubar)	130	129	508	399	383
Flattop- 25	U238(n,n')	430	440	444	282	282
	U238(n,n)	-300	-320	141	354	354
	U235(n,n')	-255	-49	324	100	100
	U235(n,gamma)	245	232	479	341	341
	U238(n,gamma)	-182	-198	129	80	80
	U235(nubar)	162	143	481	373	337
	U235(n,fission)	111	93	713	691	691
Jezebel	Pu239(n,n')	742	773	131	679	578
	Pu239(n,n)	-339	-337	101	528	393
	Pu239(n,fission)	-258	-255	303	905	549
	Pu239(n,chi)	189	189	509	217	95

Case	Main contributor	E80/J33* Substitution MF/MT	E80/J33 Perturbation S/A	JEF-3.3 =JEFF-4.0 uncertainty	ENDF/B- VIII.0 uncertainty	ENDF/B- VIII.1 uncertainty
Flattop- Pu	U238(n,n')	349	382	453	266	266
	U238(n,n)	-324	-309	125	342	342
	Pu239(n,n')	254	274	43	236	191
	Pu239(n,fission)	-239	-228	279	786	426
	Pu239(n,chi)	199	180	553	232	100
	Pu239(n,nubar)	160	159	382	270	370
	U238(n,gamma)	-157	-166	110	67	67
	Pu239(n,n)	-141	-128	35	201	156
BigTen	U238(n,gamma)	-970	-985	614	396	396
	U238(n,n')	490	501	506	267	267
	U235(n,gamma)	317	297	466	316	316
	U238(n,n)	-236	-233	126	262	262
	U238(n,fission)	211	216	390	178	178
	U235(n,nubar)	151	150	410	311	248
	U238(n,nubar)	-142	-145	232	293	293
ZEBRA- 8H	U238(n,gamma)	-1463	-1456	860	583	582
	U235(n,gamma)	327	320	446	299	299
	U238(n,fission)	207	229	394	182	182
	U238(n,nubar)	-159	-146	249	315	293
	U235(n,n')	127	38	136	43	43
	U235(n,nubar)	120	114	406	310	243
	U238(n,n')	-39	-207	1326	786	786

5. CONCLUSIONS

A set of six benchmarks representative of small fast systems is selected to perform a sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification of recent nuclear data evaluations JEFF-3.3 and 4.0, ENDF/B-VIII.0 and VIII.1. The resulting uncertainties in k_{eff} are estimated based on linear perturbation theory using the sensitivity coefficients and the covariance matrices for the corresponding nuclear data, including angular distributions. It can be concluded that the k_{eff} bias (C-E) are broadly covered by the relative uncertainties originating from the respective covariance data. However, an analysis of individual contributions shows that for some cases, library deviations between JEFF-3.3 and ENDF/B-VIII.0 are significantly higher than the respective nuclear data uncertainty contributions.

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